

**KNOWLEDGE, PRACTICES, AND ATTITUDE TOWARDS CRIMINAL JUSTICE
PROGRAM THROUGH QUALITY EDUCATION: ITS EFFECT TO WMSU
CRIMINOLOGY STUDENT'S ACADEMIC SATISFACTION AND
PROFESSIONAL CONDUCT IN SCHOOL**

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Knowledge, Practices, and Attitude Towards Criminal Justice Program Through Quality Education: Its Effect to WMSU Criminology Student's Academic Satisfaction and Professional Conduct in School

Magna Anissa A. Hayudini,* Safia E. Aming, Brenda E. Aming-Hussin, Jardine Abdulpatta, Hasanul Basariy B. Alam
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study assesses the knowledge, practices, and attitudes toward criminal justice education among criminology students at Western Mindanao State University (WMSU) and its impact on their academic satisfaction and professional conduct. Key research questions include evaluating students' knowledge, practices, attitudes, professional conduct, and academic satisfaction, and examining the effect of gender on these aspects. A non-experimental, descriptive-predictive research design was used, with stratified random sampling to select 30 criminology students (25 males, 5 females) for the academic year 2022-2023. Data collection involved a researcher-developed questionnaire validated through reliability testing. Results showed high agreement among students regarding their criminal justice education quality. The mean scores for knowledge (4.85), practices (4.73), and attitudes (4.56) indicated a strong consensus on the program's effectiveness. Professional conduct and academic satisfaction also received high mean scores of 4.82 and 5.00, respectively. Gender analysis revealed no significant differences, supporting the hypothesis that quality education positively impacts students' knowledge, practices, and attitudes toward criminal justice education. The study concludes that WMSU's criminology students strongly agree on the effectiveness of their education in terms of knowledge, practices, attitudes, professional conduct, and academic satisfaction. Recommendations include further research, continuous adherence to professional conduct, and addressing gender-based stereotypes within the program. Faculty and administrators are encouraged to monitor and support criminology students' academic and professional development to sustain high educational standards.

Keywords: *knowledge, practices and attitudes, criminal justice program, academic satisfaction, professional conduct*

Introduction

The quality education is a need everywhere in the world, hence, education is to prepare students to lead successful and fulfilling lives in the future (Hayudini et al., 2023). Nowadays, quality education is a mean of providing them with relevant educational experiences and good practices that nurture their passions, problem-solving abilities, and higher level thinking skills, including critical thinking and creativity (Hayudini et al., 2023). It may be accomplished by the best solutions that involve teachers, students, schools, family, and whole communities.

The study of Lauzon (1998), states that adult education is facing two challenges. An adult educators need to help people learn to live in harmony with the environment thus a primary goal of education is to prepare students for successful in adult life, and while our 21st century world has seen changes that no one would have envisaged even 20 years ago, the classroom and curriculum that evolved with mass education have not adapted. Meanwhile, teaching different methodologies that worked when routine jobs were in high demand still dominate.

Technology, however, is crucial for quality education to be enhanced and promoted in all schools. For many students who rely on technology on daily basis especially on coming up with research, doing assignments, and home works will be difficult to imagine anyone without internet access and devices. Therefore, technological advances have not only made the lives of students more convenient, but have allowed those other students with access to these technologies to make great strides in education. A well-known author said that the purpose in response to calls for more research on gender in digital contexts that every child should have the ability to take advantage of these technological advances (Souto et al. 2022).

A school of criminology or criminal justice in the Philippines has been showcasing its mission to maintain high-quality academic programs to meet the needs of undergraduate students. Their program offers a broad array of coursework and activities designed to provide students with the requisite preparation to become well qualified criminal justice professionals or to continue their professional education like in the law school administration, graduate, and postgraduate degree in order to encourage the pursuit of academic excellence and professional conduct in their field of expertise.

This is the main reason why the researcher would like to determine knowledge, practices and attitudes towards criminal justice education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University and its effect to their academic satisfaction and professional conduct in school.

Methodology

A non-experimental research design was used in the study particularly a type of research was utilized specifically the descriptive-predictive research method (Aming-Hayudini, Jaddani et al. 2022). The researchers did not deliberately manipulate and controlled the

participants in the study but tried to described anything that existed in the research. Meanwhile, the purpose of the researcher is mainly observed, described, and documented everything that correlates to the study. Particularly, the researcher applied evaluative descriptive design in order to collect and analyze the information relating to the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of respondents toward criminal justice education in their institution. A probability sampling was used in the study by randomly selecting the respondents in order to refrain sampling bias. Specifically, applying stratified random sampling to determine the group of respondents according to gender in terms of professional conduct they employ in their institution. The advantage of this design allowed the researcher to estimate the strength and magnitude of the sampling error or values. This research was conducted at Western Mindanao State University School particularly among criminology students under the program of the criminal justice education. This school is located at Barangay Baliwasan, Zamboanga City, Philippines.

Since the researchers employed stratified random sampling in the study, the respondents were among selected criminology students under criminal justice education for academic year 2022-2023. At least 30 criminology students were randomly selected out of the total population of the officially enrolled students confirmed at the Office of the Registrar. There were 30 selected students who answered the questionnaire. There were 25 selected male students and 5 selected female students in different levels. Like in the study of (Hayudini, Hussin et al. 2022) they used interview guide questions tool. This study used the data from the related studies in formulating the research questionnaire, therefore, the tool was made personally by the researcher subject to the validity and reliability testing procedures conducted. There were three (3) research expert validators checked and correct the constructed research questionnaire. Upon approval from the experts, the research questionnaire undergone reliability testing in two (2) consecutive intervals to pilot test the clarity and correctness of the tool. The data were randomly gathered from the 30 selected criminology students who are officially enrolled in the academic year 2022-2023 through answering the questionnaire tool given to them. Before launching, the researcher sought permission from Dean of the Western Mindanao State University and the MSU-Sulu Graduate School Dean. Upon approval, the consent letters were given to the selected criminology students who were randomly selected to answer the research questionnaire. The retrieval of the tool was on the same day of the launching to avoid changes of the idea from the respondents.

Table 1. *Statement of the Problems and its corresponding statistical tools used*

<i>Statement of the Problems</i>	<i>Statistical Tools used</i>
What is the knowledge, practices, and attitude towards criminal justice program through quality education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University?	MEAN and STANDARD DEVIATION
What is the professional conduct in school among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University?	MEAN and STANDARD DEVIATION
What is the academic satisfaction of criminology students of Western Mindanao State University?	MEAN and STANDARD DEVIATION
Is there a significant effect of the knowledge, practices, and attitudes towards criminal justice program through quality education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University when grouped according to gender?	Frequency/LOGISTICS/ SIMPLE LINEAR REGRESSION

Table 2. *Legend and Interpretation of the Likert Scale*

<i>Number</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Range</i>
1	Strongly Disagree	1 – 1.8
2	Disagree	1.9 – 2.6
3	Neither Agree nor Disagree	2.7 – 3.4
4	Agree	3.5 – 4.2
5	Strongly Agree	4.3 – 5.00

Ethical Considerations

In this research, ethical considerations were set to guide the researcher of the code of conduct in acquiring data and privacy of the respondents in this study. Appeal for consent was also provided to each participating student before they answered the questionnaire. More so, all selected participants were properly explained of the procedures on data gathering by how the questionnaire launched at them.

Results and Discussion

Table 3 shows the knowledge towards criminal justice program through quality education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University.

The result for the statement number 1 “I understand that it is vital to comprehend the duties within the legal system as a criminology student” with the mean 4.86 and standard deviation of .345 which means that majority strongly agreed. Meanwhile, statement number

2 “I understand that a criminology student must get definite instruction and equipped trainings in order to work in the criminal justice system in the future” with the mean of 4.83 and standard deviation of .379 indicates strongly agree. It shows that the knowledge towards criminal justice program through quality education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University with the total mean of 4.85 which means “Strongly Agree” and standard deviation of .351.

Table 4 shows the practices towards criminal justice program through quality education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University. The result for the statement number 1 “My contemporary criminology students integrate technology into learnings in the classroom and embrace project-based learning like investigating a scene and enforcing a law” with the mean 4.80 and standard deviation of .406 which means that majority strongly agreed. Meanwhile, statement number 2 “My contemporary criminology students apply their knowledge of the law and other academic subjects they learned” with the mean of 4.66 and standard deviation of .479 indicates strongly agree. It shows that the practices towards criminal justice program through quality education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University with the total mean of 4.73 which means “Strongly Agree” and standard deviation of .409.

Table 3. Knowledge Towards Criminal Justice Program Through Quality Education Among Criminology College Students Of Western Mindanao State University

<i>Descriptive Statistics</i>			
	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>
1. I understand that it is vital to comprehend the duties within the legal system as a criminology student.	30	4.8667	.34575
2. I understand that a criminology student must get definite instruction and equipped trainings in order to work in the criminal justice system in the future.	30	4.8333	.37905
PIA.TOTAL	30	4.8500	.35111
Valid N (listwise)	30		

Table 4. Practices Towards Criminal Justice Program Through Quality Education Among Criminology College Students Of Western Mindanao State University

<i>Descriptive Statistics</i>			
	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>
1. My contemporary criminology students integrate technology into learnings in the classroom and embrace project-based learning like investigating a scene and enforcing a law.	30	4.8000	.40684
2. My contemporary criminology students apply their knowledge of the law and other academic subjects they learned.	30	4.6667	.47946
PIB.TOTAL	30	4.7333	.40965
Valid N (listwise)	30		

Table 5 shows the attitude towards the criminal justice programs through quality education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University.

The result for statement number 1, “My contemporary criminology students are prepared to pursue a career in criminal justice education,” with a mean of 4.46 and a standard deviation of .819, which means that the majority strongly agreed. Meanwhile, statement number 2 “My contemporary criminology students behave inside the school premises with just, respect and courage” with the mean of 4.66 and standard deviation of .606 indicates strongly agree. It shows that the attitude towards criminal justice program through quality education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University with the total mean of 4.56 which means “Strongly Agree” and standard deviation of .691.

Table 5. Attitude Towards Criminal Justice Program Through Quality Education Among Criminology College Students Of Western Mindanao State University

<i>Descriptive Statistics</i>			
	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>
1. My contemporary criminology students are prepared to pursue a career in criminal justice education.	30	4.4667	.81931
2. My contemporary criminology students behave inside the school premises with just, respect and courage.	30	4.6667	.60648
PIC.TOTAL	30	4.5667	.69149
Valid N (listwise)	30		

Table 6 shows the professional conduct towards criminal justice program through quality education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University.

The result for the statement number 1 “As a criminology student, I shall foster high concepts of citizenry and leadership in the class and at school campus” with the mean 4.66 and standard deviation of .546 which means that majority strongly agreed. Meanwhile, statement number 2 “As a criminology student, I shall know my field of profession with full of responsibility to help our professors in implementing rules and regulations in school” with the mean of 5.0 and standard deviation of .000 indicates strongly agree. For statement number 3 “As a criminology student, I shall develop thinking skills by learning how to navigate social, emotional, and ethical realms inside the school premises” with mean 4.93 and standard deviation of .253 which means “Strongly Agree”. For statement number 4 “As a criminology student, I shall understand the methods and culture applied in this profession with due process of law” with mean of 4.56 and standard deviation of .776 which means “strongly agree” and lastly, statement number 5 “As a criminology student, I shall acquire a wide range of vital skills, good conduct and attitudes inside the school” with the mean of 5.0 and standard deviation of .000 which indicates “strongly agree”.

It shows that the professional conduct towards criminal justice program through quality education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University has the total mean of 4.82 which means “Strongly Agree” and standard deviation of .289.

Table 6. Professional conduct towards criminal justice program through quality education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University

<i>Descriptive Statistics</i>			
	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>
1. As a criminology student, I shall foster high concepts of citizenry and leadership in the class and at school campus.	30	4.6667	.54667
2. As a criminology student, I shall know my field of profession with full of responsibility to help our professors in implementing rules and regulations in school.	30	5.0000	.00000
3. As a criminology student, I shall develop thinking skills by learning how to navigate social, emotional, and ethical realms inside the school premises.	30	4.9333	.25371
4. As a criminology student, I shall understand the methods and culture applied in this profession with due process of law.	30	4.5000	.77682
5. As a criminology student, I shall acquire a wide range of vital skills, good conduct and attitudes inside the school.	30	5.0000	.00000
P2.TOTAL	30	4.8200	.28935
Valid N (listwise)	30		

Table 7 shows the academic satisfaction towards criminal justice program through quality education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University.

The result for the item number 1 “School Policies and guidelines implementation” with the mean 5.00 and standard deviation of .000 which means that majority strongly agreed. Meanwhile, item number 2 “Educational experiences, bench marking and school activities” with the mean of 5.00 and standard deviation of .000 indicates strongly agree. For item number 3 “Expert and skilled professors” with mean 5.00 and standard deviation of .000 which means “Strongly Agree”. For statement number 4 “Curriculum Update” with mean of 5.00 and standard deviation of .000 which means “strongly agree” and lastly, item number 5 “Quality Assurance like results of Board rating and Program Accreditation and Compliance with the mean of 5.00 and standard deviation of .000 which indicates “strongly agree”.

It shows that the academic satisfaction towards criminal justice program through quality education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University has the total mean of 5.00 which means “Strongly Agree” and standard deviation of .000.

<i>Descriptive Statistics</i>			
<i>Academic Satisfaction</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>
1. School Policies and guidelines implementation.	30	5.0000	.00000
2. Educational experiences, bench marking and school activities.	30	5.0000	.00000
3. Expert and skilled professors.	30	5.0000	.00000
4. Curriculum Update	30	5.0000	.00000
5. Quality Assurance like results of Board rating and Program Accreditation and Compliance	30	5.0000	.00000
P3.TOTAL	30	5.0000	.00000
Valid N (listwise)	30		

Table 8 shows the number of selected respondents in the study that revealed the mean of 1.166 out of 30 selected criminology students of Western Mindanao State University.

<i>Descriptive Statistics</i>			
	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>
Gender	30	1.1667	.37905
Total	30	1.1667	.37905
Valid N (listwise)	30		

Table 9 shows the gender in the study that revealed 25 of them are males with percentage of 83.3 and 5 of them are females which percentage of 16.7 out of 30 selected criminology students of Western Mindanao State University.

		<i>TOTAL</i>			
		<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Valid Percent</i>	<i>Cumulative Percent</i>
Valid	MALE	25	83.3	83.3	83.3
	FEMALE	5	16.7	16.7	100.0
	Total	30	100.0	100.0	

This shows the knowledge, practices, and attitude towards criminal justice program through quality education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University according to gender with the P-Value of .000 which means the findings of the study failed to reject the hypothesis.

<i>Model</i>		<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>ANOVA^a</i>			<i>Sig.</i>	<i>Decision</i>
			<i>Df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>		
1	Regression	3.217	1	3.217	94.838	.000 ^b	This study FAILED TO REJECT the hypothesis
	Residual	.950	28	.034			
	Total	4.167	29				

a. Dependent Variable: GENDER
 b. Predictors: (Constant), overallkpa

A non-experimental research design was used in the study particularly descriptive-predictive research design (Hayudini 2018). The researcher did not deliberately manipulate and controlled the participants in the study but tried to described anything that existed in the research. Meanwhile, the purpose of the researcher is mainly observed, described, and documented everything that correlates to the study. A probability sampling was used in the study by randomly selecting the respondents in order to refrain sampling bias. Specifically, applying stratified random sampling to determine the group of respondents according to gender in terms of professional conduct they employ in their institution. This research was conducted at Western Mindanao State University School particularly among criminology students under the program of the criminal justice education. This school is located at Barangay Baliwasan, Zamboanga City, Philippines. the respondents were among selected criminology students under criminal justice education for academic year 2022-2023. At least 30 criminology students were randomly selected out of the total population of the officially enrolled students confirmed at the Office of the Registrar. There were 30 selected students who answered the questionnaire. There were 25 selected male students and 5 selected female students in different levels. The tool was made personally by the researcher subject to the validity and reliability testing procedures conducted. There were three (3) research expert validators checked and correct the constructed research questionnaire. Upon approval from the experts, the research questionnaire undergone reliability testing in two (2) consecutive intervals to pilot test the clarity and correctness of the tool. The statistical tools were employed using mean, standard deviation, frequency, percentage, and logistics or simple linear regression.

Discussion

Based on the analysis and interpretation of the data revealed the following findings. The study used descriptive statistics such weighted mean as a tool of analysis of the data collected (Aming-Hayudini & Kasim, 2022). This research examines the interrelationship of tripartite variables such as knowledge, practice, attitudes, academic satisfaction, and performance (Pangandaman, Ortega et al., 2021).

The data showed that the knowledge of criminal justice programs through quality education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University had a total mean of 4.85, which resulted in “Strongly Agree” and a standard deviation of .351. As such, students do not lack knowledge (Diamla, Mejia et al. 2020).

It revealed that the practices towards criminal justice programs through quality education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University had a mean of 4.73, resulting in “Strongly Agree” and a standard deviation of .409.

It revealed the attitude towards criminal justice programs through quality education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University had a total mean of 4.56, which resulted in “Strongly Agree” and a standard deviation of .691.

It revealed the professional conduct towards the criminal justice program through quality education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University has a total mean of 4.82, which resulted in “Strongly Agree” and a standard deviation of .289.

It revealed the academic satisfaction towards criminal justice program through quality education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University has a total mean of 5.00, which resulted in “Strongly Agree” and a standard deviation of .000.

It revealed the number of selected respondents in the study with the mean of 1.166 of 30 selected criminology students of Western Mindanao State University, the gender in the study revealed 25 of them were males with percentage of 83.3 and 5 of them were females which percentage of 16.7 of 30 selected criminology students of Western Mindanao State University.

It also revealed the knowledge, practices, and attitudes towards criminal justice programs through quality education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University according to gender with a P-Value of .000, which means the hypothesis is accepted or failed or rejected.

Conclusion

The researchers conclude that the knowledge of criminal justice programs through quality education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University resulted in “Strongly Agree”. However, it revealed that the practices towards criminal justice programs through quality education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University had shown the result of “Strongly Agree.” Likewise, it also revealed the attitude towards criminal justice programs through quality education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University resulted in “Strongly Agree”. This study concluded the professional conduct towards criminal justice program through quality education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University resulted to “Strongly Agree” and academic satisfaction towards criminal justice program through quality education among criminology college students of Western Mindanao State University revealed “Strongly Agree.” The research that has been done aims to analyze the effect of the faculty's work environment on their students and vice versa. Moreover, it revealed the number of selected respondents in the study with 25 males and 5 females with a total of 30 selected criminology students of Western Mindanao State University strongly agreed with the knowledge, practices, and attitudes towards criminal justice program through quality education which hypothesis is accepted or failed to reject it.

Research Agenda: If possible, another study will be conducted in the future. The students shall continue to adhere to the knowledge, practices, and attitudes towards the criminal justice program in their school. The students shall strictly follow professional conduct and ethics in the school premises. The students shall lead an example to their lower contemporaries in dealing with proper conduct in the school. The students shall embed the importance of academic matters in the school to facilitate more learning and skills.

Research Policies: Western Mindanao State University may continually impose policy mandated inside the campus. Professors may monitor and supervise criminology students if possible inside the campus. The School Administrator may monitor the knowledge, practice and attitude of criminology students in relation to professional conduct in school. The School Administrator may continue instilling of proper knowledge, practice and attitude of criminology students in relation to academic satisfaction in school. The school professors may correct the stereotype discrimination on gender of the criminology students in the said program.

Research Problems: The effect of criminology program to Senior High School students. The increased number of enrollees of female students in criminology courses. Gender awareness on criminal justice program among students. Academic satisfaction of criminology students on the new curriculum. Effect of ROTC in college criminology program.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Magna Anissa A. Hayudini

Mindanao State University – Philippines

Safia E. Aming

Mindanao State University – Philippines

Brenda E. Aming-Hussin

Mindanao State University – Philippines

Jardine Abdulpatta

Mindanao State University – Philippines

Hasanul Basariy B. Alam

Mindanao State University – Philippines